

Nanoscale evidence for Ti-bearing hematite and coupled Fe–S–O–H oxidation in Chang'e-6 impact melts

Q. Fang^{1,2*}, K. Gao¹, L. Yang¹, Z. Wang¹, B. Gault², Z.-Q. Chen¹

1. State Key Laboratory of Geomicrobiology and Environmental Changes, Hubei Provincial Key Laboratory of Planetary Geology and Deep-Space Exploration, School of Earth Sciences, China University of Geosciences, 430074 Wuhan, China

2. Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials, Max-Planck-Str.1, 40237 Düsseldorf, Germany

*Email address: qian.fang@cug.edu.cn

The lunar surface is traditionally characterized as a highly reducing environment dominated by space weathering processes that drive volatile loss and iron reduction. Although recent sample returns have identified localized ferric iron phases, the precise micro-environments and mechanisms responsible for impact-driven oxidation remain poorly constrained. Here, we report a highly oxidized, volatile-bearing mineral assemblage preserved within a surface impact melt on a feldspathic grain from the Chang'e-6 (CE-6) farside regolith, investigated via a correlated TEM, EELS, Atom Probe Tomography (APT), and NanoSIMS workflow.

The dominant oxidized phase in this assemblage is identified as Ti-bearing hematite. Electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS) of the Fe L-edge reveals a distinct shift to higher energy (709.5 eV) and a low L3/L2 white-line intensity ratio consistent with Fe³⁺-dominated oxides, definitively distinguishing it from ilmenite or magnetite. Texturally, the Ti-bearing phases occur as subparallel acicular lamellae within a hematite-rich matrix. This specific geometry suggests structurally controlled segregation or sub-solidus exsolution during the rapid quenching of a high-temperature, highly oxidized melt domain.

Atomic-scale reconstructions by APT demonstrate that this oxidation was not limited to iron. The morphologically distinct FeO-rich domains are co-enriched in Fe, Ti, TiO, SO, and FeOH molecular ions. Radial distribution functions confirm that sulfur in this domain is spatially correlated with transition metals (Fe, Ti, Mg, Mn) and anti-correlated with Ca, indicating structural incorporation of oxidized sulfur within the Ti-hematite matrix rather than preservation as discrete sulfides. Additionally, NanoSIMS mapping and APT reveal spatially decoupled volatile sinks within the same melt layer, including Ca–S-rich fissure

infillings and nanoscale Cl–P–K-rich domains consistent with apatite-group phases.

These observations indicate that the CE-6 impact melt acted as a transient geochemical microreactor. The crystallization of Ti-hematite, coupled with the nanoscale partitioning of oxidized sulfur and the localized retention of halogens and hydroxyl-related species, demonstrates that hypervelocity impacts on the lunar farside can drive extreme, localized Fe–Ti–S–O–H chemical reorganization. This provides a new mechanistic framework for understanding how highly oxidized and volatile-bearing signatures can be generated and preserved on airless bodies.